

The pLoc_bal-mGneg Predictor is a Powerful Web-Server for Identifying the Subcellular Localization of Gram-Negative Bacterial Proteins based on their Sequences Information Alone

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Running Title: Showcase for pLoc_bal-mGneg

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Recently a very powerful web-server has been developed for predicting the subcellular localization of Gram-negative bacterial proteins purely according to their sequences information for the multi-label systems [1], in which a same protein may appear or move between two or more location sites and hence its ID (identification) needs two or more labels for distinction, namely the “multi-label mark” [2].

The web-server is called as “pLoc_bal-mGneg”, where “bal” means that the predictor has been treated by balancing or quasi-balancing out the training dataset [3-9], and “m” means that the predictor is with the capacity to study the multi-label systems. How the web-server is working can be clearly seen via the showcase below.

Clicking the link at http://www.jci-bioinfo.cn/pLoc_bal-mGneg/, you will see the top page of the pLoc_bal-mGneg web-server prompted on your computer’s screen (Figure 1). Then, just simply following the commands given in the Step 2 and Step 3 of [4], you will see Figure 2 on the screen of your computer. For example, if using the query protein sequences in the Example window as the input, after clicking the Submit button, the corresponding detailed prediction results were given in [4]. As you can see from there: nearly all the success rates achieved by the web-server for the Gram-negative bacterial proteins in each of the 8 subcellular locations are within the range of 98-100%, which is far beyond the reach of any of its counterparts.

Figure 1. A semi screenshot for the top page of pLoc_bal-mGneg (Adapted from [4] with permission).

Protein ID	Subcellular location or locations
>P22340	2
>P04032	8
>P04825	1, 3
>P22251	4, 6

Figure 2. A semi screenshot for the webpage obtained by following Step 3 of Section 3.5 (Adapted from [4] with permission).

In addition to the advantages of high accuracy and easy to use, the web-server has been constructed by strictly observing the “Chou’s 5-steps rule” and hence bears the following fantastic merits as agreed and supported by many investigators (see, e.g., [10-91] as well as three comprehensive review papers [2, 92, 93]): (1) crystal clear in logic development, (2) completely transparent in operation, (3) easily to repeat the reported results by other investigators, (4) with high potential in stimulating other sequence-analyzing methods, and (5) very convenient to be used by the majority of experimental scientists.

Besides, the approach [94-96] of PseAAC (Pseudo Amino Acid Composition) has also been applied during developing the web-server predictor. It is a very powerful approach for representing the protein samples by catching their special or key features, as done by many scientists as well [97-222].

Furthermore, the IHTS (Inserting Hypothetical Training Samples) treatment has also been applied to balance or quasi-balance out the training dataset [57, 60, 84].

For the amazing and awesome roles of the “5-steps rule” and general “PseAAC” in driving proteome, genome analyses and drug development, see a series of recent papers [2, 93, 223-233] where both the “5-steps rule” and the general “PseAAC” as well as their huge impacts have been very impressively recollected at different angles or from varieties of aspects.

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